

The language of Seidr.

Words starting with the letter A:

English	Seidr
A	Anda
And	Andana
Above	Indascana
Absolute	Ebretonda
Absorb	Boba
Accelerate	Askadana
Accept	Trinda
Activate	Activatana
Actual	Brindalunda
Add	Pluska
Admiral	Navabrenda
Adult	Lothka
Advanced	Potrana
Affair	Freyja
After	Afternium
Age	Aganium
Aggressive	Angrbuda
Air	Aeronda
All	Odina
Alpha	Alfabrana
Alternative	Vindabrunda
Amazon	Herculia (the jungle)
Amused	Angrboda
Angel	Angelica
Angle	Bruenaska
Angry	Angr
Animal	Aesir
Aspect	Aesir
Annual	Yarvanda
Anonymous	Speliskorna
Answer	Liska
Anti	Christalanta
Antique	Eldgamalia
Apart	Freya
Apparent	Dentalenska
Applaud	Svidium
Appointment	Truskaskarna
Approximate	Que
Arch	Arkana
Architect	Arkanadana
Area	Guedtae

Argument	Gruskarunda
Arm	Heliaxana
Army	Hoplitana
Armour	Platia
Arrange	Yinda
Arrow	Buitska
As	Eiscaea
Ash	Umbra
Ask	Dindana
Ass	Anium
Assemble	Frigania
Associate	Eternium
At	Aetrana
Athlete	Olympiadana
Atrocity	Trislapuska
Attic	Wodnium
Attraction	Frigga
August	Augustus
Australia	Aliagardium
Automatic	Fiskarna
Average	Avangarda

Magic word and curse word:

English	Seidr
The magic word tada	Taedna
The curse word tadum	Taeduemna